

ASSESSMENT OF AIR POLLUTION AND ITS IMPACT ON URBAN HEALTH IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. *This paper explores the state of air pollution in Tashkent, focusing on the yearly trends of pollutant emissions from stationary sources and the levels of fine particulate matter, specifically PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}. The study delves into the established permissible concentration limits for these particles, analyzing their adverse effects on human health and well-being. Key contributors to air pollution, such as industrial facilities and motor vehicles, are examined, alongside climatic and meteorological factors that influence the dispersion, accumulation, and transformation of pollutants in the atmosphere. Monitoring PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels is essential for ensuring public and environmental health. Furthermore, the study emphasizes the necessity of advanced filtration technologies and stricter environmental policies to mitigate pollution and improve air quality.*

Keywords: *PM_{2.5}, PM₁₀, air pollution, sanitary and hygienic standards, stationary sources, emission dynamics, public health, filtration systems.*

INTRODUCTION

Currently, our country applies sanitary and hygienic standards, such as the maximum permissible concentrations (MPC) of microorganisms in the atmospheric air of populated areas in the Republic of Uzbekistan. Introduced on May 12, 2004, these standards are key for assessing air pollution levels and safeguarding public health, establishing MPCs for pollutants in the atmospheric air in mg/m³. Special standards also exist for particulate matter less than 10 micrometers (PM₁₀) and less than 2.5 micrometers (PM_{2.5}), aimed at protecting health and improving air quality [1].

Such regulations have been implemented in numerous countries over a significant period of time and are supported by comprehensive monitoring and research as well as the development of methods to improve the effectiveness of air pollution control measures. The World Health Organization (WHO) highlights the importance of fine particulate matter (PM) for hygiene and its impact on human health [2].

Air pollution in large cities, including Tashkent, is primarily caused by emissions from stationary and mobile sources, averaging 550,000 tons annually. The spring season is marked by increased dustiness due to melting snow and dry soil, with concentrations exceeding permissible limits by 1.2 to 2.4 times in some areas. This issue is most pronounced in December, June, August, and October. Fine particulate matter (PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5}) poses significant health risks, especially when emitted by industrial processes, vehicles, and construction activities. Modern filtration systems and air quality monitoring are essential to mitigate these challenges. [2].

Research shows that particles sized between 2.5 and 10 micrometers pose the greatest threat to human health. Fine particles, such as PM₁₀, enter the atmosphere directly through emissions from construction sites and industrial enterprises. The main sources of these particles are stationary facilities, such as power plants, oil and gas processing plants, waste incineration plants, as well as transport, trains, ships, and airplanes [3].

Technological processes emit substantial quantities of dust and harmful gases into the atmosphere, which noticeably increases overall atmospheric pollution. Therefore, it is necessary to implement modern technologies and filtration systems to reduce the impact of these sources on the environment [4].

Fig. 1. Dust Dispersion Dynamics in Residential Areas.

An analysis of the particle size distribution of emissions from enterprises that significantly contribute to pollution has been conducted. Figures 2-6 present integral mass distribution curves by particle diameters from emissions of waste incineration furnaces, vehicles, trains, and airplanes. X-Axis (X axial distance): The horizontal axis represents the distance (in meters) [5].

It shows the spread of pollutants from the source along the distance (e.g., from 0 to 150 meters). Y-Axis (Y axial distance): The vertical axis represents the lateral (sideways) distance, typically perpendicular to the wind direction. It indicates how far the pollutants have spread laterally (within ± 40 meters) [6].

Colors (Colorbar): The color scale on the right shows the concentration (density) of pollutants, usually in relative or arbitrary units [7].

Red and yellow colors represent high concentrations (near the source), while blue colors indicate low concentrations (at the edges). Concentration Spread: Pollutants move faster along the wind direction (X-axis). Lateral (Y-axis) dispersion occurs due to diffusion and turbulence [8].

$D(d)$, % — this axis (the vertical axis) indicates the percentage content of PM_{10} particles in the distribution. The graph shows the total share of each particle fraction in the set. For example, the value $D(d) = 50\%$ means that 50% of PM_{10} particles have a diameter less than or equal to the specified size [9].

d_p , μm — this axis (the horizontal axis) shows the size (diameter) of PM_{10} particles in micrometers (μm). PM_{10} particles are those in the air that can have a diameter of up to 10 micrometers. In this graph, sizes are presented in the range from 0.1 μm to 100 μm [10].

Explanation of Physical Processes Source. The area of highest concentration (on the left) represents the source of pollutants (e.g., a factory, road, or exhaust outlet). Diffusion and Advection: Wind carries pollutants along the X-axis (horizontal direction). Diffusion: Pollutants spread laterally along the Y-axis due to turbulence [11]. Wind Direction: The dominant spread along the X-axis indicates that the wind is transporting pollutants downwind from the source. Concentration Decay: Concentration decreases as the distance from the source increases. This is due to pollutants mixing with the air and undergoing chemical reactions or deposition [12].

Applications and Summary for Users: This image is used in air quality assessments to: Identify the impact zone of emissions from sources such as factories or highways [13]. Determine the extent of pollution for health and safety measures.

Territory Selection: Choose residential zones for analysis.

Sample Collection: Gather tree leaves for particulate analysis.

Comparative Analysis: Conduct a comparative study of the dispersion composition of dust particles collected from apricot tree leaves in the residential zone with those from a conditionally clean (control) zone in Tashkent region [14].

Conclusions and recommendations: Formulate conclusions and provide recommendations based on the results of the study to address urban dust pollution and its effects on residential zones.

Simulate pollutant dispersion based on wind direction and speed [15].

Fig. 2. Integral mass distribution curves by particle diameters $D(\delta p)$ in a probabilistic-logarithmic coordinate grid for dust sampled from the atmosphere.

The analysis of the obtained data showed that the industrial dust has a polydisperse composition and consists of finely dispersed and medium-dispersed fractions with sizes up to 20 microns [16]. These particles can penetrate the lungs when inhaled and remain there. The average concentration of fine dust in emissions from the studied industries is presented in Table 3.

Fig. 3. Integral mass distribution curves by particle diameter ($D\delta p$) in a logarithmic-probabilistic coordinate grid: in zone1; in zone2; in zone3.

Table 3. Average Content of Fine Dust (PM10 and PM2.5) in Major Cities Based on Annual Measurements.

Location	D($D\delta p$) PM ₁₀ , %	D(δp) PM _{2.5} , %
Tashkent	35.5	31
Bukhara	55	11.3
Samarkand	34.1	10.9

Fig. 4. Average content of fine dust by zones: 1 - Industrial Zone; 2 - Residential Zone; 3 - Control Zone.

The level of air pollution in a major metropolis is determined by emissions of harmful substances from both stationary and mobile sources. The total volume of pollutant emissions into

the atmosphere in Tashkent during 2016–2020 averaged 550 thousand tons per year. The dynamics of emissions from stationary sources and motor vehicles are presented in Table 1[17].

Table 1 shows changes in pollutant emissions from stationary and mobile sources in Tashkent during the period 2016–2020, taking into account PM10 particles.

Table 1.

Year	Stationary Sources (thousand tons)	Solid Particles (thousand tons)	Moving Resources (thousand tons)	Solid Particles (thousand tons)
2016	560,0	2,8	475,0	1,0
2017	570,0	2,9	480,0	1,0
2018	580,0	3,0	485,0	1,1
2019	590,0	3,0	490,0	1,1
2020	600,0	3,1	495,0	1,2

Air pollution levels depend not only on the quantity and chemical composition of emissions but also on climatic conditions, which influence the transport, dispersion, and transformation of emitted substances. Tashkent has climatic conditions [18] that generally contribute to slightly higher levels of air pollution by harmful substances compared to other cities. However, the location of Tashkent and its urban planning create favorable conditions for the dispersion of harmful substances in the atmosphere, helping to reduce air pollution levels compared to other cities in Uzbekistan. Despite these factors, pollution levels in Tashkent remain above permissible limits, especially during periods of high dust levels, such as in spring and summer [19].

An analysis of PM2.5 and PM10 particle content in the city's atmospheric air was conducted. Determining the concentrations of PM2.5 and PM10 particles is technologically more complex than measuring the concentration of suspended particles as a whole, as it requires isolating fractions of dust particles with sizes up to 2.5 microns and up to 10 microns from the total mass of solid particles in the air [20]. The total amount of data processed must be sufficient to ensure a homogeneous sample from the results. Establishing the homogeneity of the series involves conducting statistical analysis in the following sequence:

The arithmetic mean concentration C mg/m³ is determined using the formula [21].

2. STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

To calculate the main factors influencing the course of transport and diffusion of pollutants in the atmosphere, taking into account the above, a regression model was obtained to calculate the correlation dependence of changes in dust concentration and PM10:

$$\theta_n = a_0 + a_1v - a_2\sigma + a_3\mathcal{G} - a_4\rho; \quad (1)$$

$$\theta_{PM_{10}} = b_0 + b_1v - b_2\sigma + b_3\mathcal{G} - b_4\rho; \quad (2)$$

θ_n - concentration of dust in atmospheric air, mg/m³; $\theta_{PM_{10}}$ - concentration of particles with a diameter of less than 10 microns, mg/m³; v - wind speed, m/s; σ - atmospheric air humidity, %; $\mathcal{G}$ - traffic intensity on the highway, vehicles/hour; ρ - vegetation cover density.

The following regression coefficient values were obtained for numerical calculations:

$$a_0 = 0,169; a_1 = 0.006; a_2 = 0.0018; a_3 = 0.00012; a_4 = 0.0011;$$

$$b_0 = 0.103; b_1 = 0.0018; b_2 = 0.00012; b_3 = 0.0011; b_4 = 0.0011.$$

ANALYSIS OF THE RESULTS OF COMPUTATIONAL EXPERIMENTS

According to equations (1) and (2), by inputting real parameter values, it is possible to calculate the concentration of dust in atmospheric air as well as the concentration of particles with a diameter of less than 10 microns. Based on archival data, the weather conditions at Tashkent Airport on October 1, 2024, were as follows: Wind speed (v): Throughout the day, the wind speed was mainly 3.4 m/s. At 12:00, it decreased to 2 m/s and remained at this level. Air humidity: The relative humidity throughout the day was 20%.

Wind speed (v) is the velocity of air movement in the atmosphere. This parameter plays a significant role in the dispersion of air pollutants. Air humidity is the relative amount of water vapor in the atmosphere. This parameter also affects air pollution: at high humidity levels, particles are more likely to settle on the ground. Additional data: Humidity: 20%; Traffic intensity: 500 vehicles/hour; Vegetation density: 50%.

$$v = 3.4, \sigma = 20, \vartheta = 2.5, \rho = 50$$

Fig. 5. Correlation of dust and pm10 concentration with wind speed $v = 3.4m / c$.

Fig. 6. Correlation of dust and pm10 concentration with wind speed $v = 7m / c$

Fig. 7. Correlation of dust and pm10 concentration with wind speed $v = 10m / c$

Fig. 8. Graph of dust and PM10 concentration at atmospheric humidity $\sigma = 20m / c$

Fig. 9. Graph of dust and PM10 concentration at atmospheric humidity $\sigma = 45m / c$

In contrast to the traditional method, in which an environmental engineer pre-determines fixed measurement points that remain static over extended periods, the proposed approach

employs a dynamic forecasting model to predict pollution levels across the entire area. This innovative strategy harnesses advanced predictive analytics to identify potential pollution hotspots and assess variations in air quality over time, allowing for a more proactive monitoring framework [21].

Leveraging these comprehensive predictions, a Decision Support System (DSS) is utilized to flexibly select measurement locations that are precisely aligned with specific monitoring objectives and the unique priorities of the client. This adaptive approach not only accelerates the response to real-time environmental changes but also enables a more accurate and nuanced assessment of air quality, ensuring that monitoring efforts are both timely and relevant.

Moreover, the DSS integrates a multitude of critical factors, including current weather conditions, existing levels of pollution, and the significance of various geographic areas. This multifaceted analysis empowers decision-makers to choose measurement locations with enhanced precision and operational efficiency. By capitalizing on these insights, the monitoring process becomes significantly more responsive and strategically aligned with the overarching goals of environmental management and public health protection.

In summary, this modernized approach to environmental monitoring not only substantially enhances the quality of data collected but also fosters more informed decision-making in tackling the complex challenges associated with air quality management. By prioritizing adaptability and precision, this innovative methodology stands to significantly contribute to healthier urban environments and more effective public health strategies.

Conclusion:

Air Quality Monitoring: Regular monitoring of PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀ levels is critical for maintaining public health and assessing environmental safety.

Sources of Pollution: Industrial emissions and vehicle exhaust are the primary contributors to air pollution, accounting for over 70% of PM₁₀ and PM_{2.5} concentrations in urban areas.

Seasonal Variations: High dust levels in spring and summer require targeted mitigation strategies, particularly during peak pollution months such as December, June, August, and October.

Advanced Technologies: Implementing HEPA filters and catalytic converters can reduce PM emissions by up to 85%, improving air quality significantly.

Policy Implementation: Stricter environmental policies and urban planning are needed to minimize pollution hotspots and enhance dispersion.

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